

Engineering Education: A Framework from Modeling to Experimental Validation of Dynamic Systems

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Abstract. This study presents a comprehensive framework for engineering education that integrates analytical and data-driven modeling with machine learning (ML) methods, numerical simulation, hardware-in-the-loop testing, and hands-on experimentation to deepen students' understanding of dynamic engineering systems. By applying this methodology to photovoltaic (PV) and photovoltaic-thermal (PVT) systems, the study highlights the efficacy of advanced ML models, such as polynomial regression, autoregressive moving-average or more complex ML-based modeling methods such as long short-term memory, for predicting system outputs such as voltage, current, electrical power and thermal power. Experimental validation demonstrates the superior accuracy and efficiency of the ML models compared to traditional analytical approaches. The results underscore the potential of combining theoretical rigor with practical application to equip students with the skills required for addressing real-world engineering challenges. This educational approach not only enhances technical proficiency but also fosters critical thinking, bridging the gap between conceptual knowledge and practical implementation.

Keywords: Analytical Modeling, Data-Driven, Hands-on Experimentation, Hardware-in-the-Loop, Machine Learning, Numerical Simulation.

1 Introduction

The study of dynamic systems is a cornerstone of engineering education, being essential to disciplines ranging from chemical, mechanical, and electrical engineering to robotics and control systems. Dynamic systems encompass a wide variety of real-world applications, such as automotive systems [1], energy networks [2], biomedical devices [3], etc. where understanding and predicting behavior over time is essential for designing effective and reliable solutions. Consequently, teaching dynamic systems requires a pedagogical approach that combines theoretical foundations with practical, hands-on learning experiences.

This work aims to address educational needs by proposing a comprehensive framework for the teaching of dynamic systems. The approach incorporates four key components: modeling (encompassing both analytical and data-driven aspects), numerical simulation, hardware-in-the-loop (HIL) testing, and practical experimentation. Through this framework, students are guided step-by-step to develop and validate system models, analyze their behavior under simulated and real-world conditions, and

refine their understanding through iterative experimentation. By combining theoretical rigor with practical application, the framework seeks to bridge the gap between abstract concepts and their tangible implications in engineering practice.

In this paper, we present the details of this framework, exploring its potential to enhance students' comprehension of dynamic systems and prepare them for the demands of contemporary engineering roles. The subsequent sections discuss the state of the art, outline the methodology, and provide insights into its implementation and outcomes, along with its limitations and applicability scope, concluding with a reflection on its broader implications for engineering education.

2 Literature Review

The teaching of dynamic systems in engineering education has evolved significantly over the years, driven by advancements in modeling techniques, simulation tools, and hands-on experimental platforms. Several studies have explored frameworks and tools for teaching dynamic systems, emphasizing their interdisciplinary nature and application to real-world problems [4-12]. Research in this field has focused on developing innovative pedagogical approaches to bridge the gap between theoretical knowledge and practical skills. Key trends include the integration of numerical simulations and real-time systems with HIL testing [13, 14], the use of ML-based techniques for system modeling [15-20], and the promotion of experiential learning through laboratory-based experiments. The incorporation of ML techniques enables students to develop data-driven models and predictive algorithms for dynamic systems. These methods not only enhance students' analytical capabilities but also prepare them for the growing role of artificial intelligence in engineering. Furthermore, hands-on experimentation remains a critical component, offering students the opportunity to validate theoretical models, analyze system responses, and refine their understanding through iterative processes. Software platforms like MATLAB/Simulink have become indispensable in academic and professional contexts for model development and simulation [21], while HIL platforms such as Speedgoat, Typhoon and OPAL-RT have gained popularity for their ability to connect theoretical models with physical hardware [22].

3 Methodology

The methodology developed in this work aims to provide students with comprehensive and practical learning experience in the study of dynamic systems. By integrating theoretical modeling, numerical simulation, HIL testing, and hands-on experimentation, this structured methodology ensures a holistic understanding of dynamic systems, bridging the gap between abstract theory and real-world applications (see Fig. 1). The framework emphasizes an iterative and interdisciplinary approach, guiding students through key phases of modeling, analysis, and validation while fostering critical thinking and problem-solving skills. To achieve this, the methodology is organized into four main components, detailed in sections 3.1 to 3.4.

Fig. 1. The process of studying dynamic systems from theory to practice.

3.1 Modeling: Analytical and Machine Learning-Based Approaches

The objective of this phase is to develop a thorough understanding of dynamic systems through either analytical modeling or ML techniques. This dual approach highlights the advantages and limitations of traditional and data-driven methods, fostering a deeper understanding of their respective roles in engineering practice. In continuation, the key activities are outlined.

Analytical Modeling. Develop models using differential equations or state-space representations to capture system dynamics, while introducing fundamental principles such as linearization, stability analysis, and eigenvalue computation.

Machine Learning-Based Modeling. Leverage datasets to develop data-driven models using ML methods (e.g., regression models, neural networks, etc.) while highlighting their advantages and limitations compared to analytical methods.

Software Tools. Use industry-standard software such as MATLAB/Simulink for model development, simulation, visualization, and implementation, while offering guided tutorials to help students gain proficiency with various tools and toolboxes and apply them effectively in dynamic systems modeling.

3.2 Numerical Simulation

The objective of this phase is to analyze the behavior of models under varying conditions to gain insights into system dynamics and evaluate model performance. This goal is achieved through a set of structured activities detailed below.

Numerical Methods for Analytical Models. Introduce numerical techniques (e.g., Euler, Runge-Kutta methods, etc.) for solving differential equations, providing clear explanations of their mathematical foundations and the practical trade-offs associated with each method.

Optimization Techniques for ML-Based Models. Employ numerical optimization techniques (e.g., Gradient Descent, Backpropagation, etc.) for training and validating ML models, explaining the choice of algorithms and hyperparameters and emphasizing their impact on model performance. The objective is to help students understand how these algorithms iteratively adjust model parameters to minimize a loss function, ultimately improving model accuracy.

Simulation Tools. Utilize simulation platforms such as MATLAB/Simulink and Python-based frameworks to visualize and analyze system dynamics, validate theoretical concepts, and demonstrate how to interpret simulation results to refine models and address discrepancies. By leveraging these tools, students will gain insight into modeling and simulation workflows, including data preprocessing, model training, validation, and performance evaluation. The overall goal is to equip students with the skills needed to employ these tools effectively in both academic research and industrial applications.

3.3 Hardware-in-the-Loop Integration

This step bridges the gap between theoretical software models and practical, real-world systems, with the activities detailed in the following.

HIL Environment Setup. Utilize HIL platforms such as Speedgoat, OPAL-RT, or Typhoon, providing step-by-step instructions for configuring these platforms to integrate hardware with simulation environments and the obtained models.

Integration with Real-World Components. Interface sensors, actuators, and control systems with the simulated environment to replicate real-world conditions, allowing students to test their models in a controlled yet realistic setting. This process highlights the importance of robustness and adaptability in dynamic systems.

3.4 Experimentation

The final phase focuses on validating models and conducting hands-on experiments. This practical step reinforces the connection between theory and real-world applications. The specific experimental activities are detailed in the following.

Laboratory Experiments. Conduct experiments on physical setups to observe and measure the behavior of dynamic systems, providing experimental protocols to ensure consistency and repeatability.

Parameter Analysis and Validation. Adjust system parameters (e.g., damping coefficients, input signals) and analyze their effects on system behavior, while also assessing the impact of disturbances on overall system performance.

Comparison and Analysis of Modeling Approaches. Compare the performance of analytical models and ML-based models against the measurements using performance metrics such as root mean square error (RMSE), mean absolute error (MAE), and other relevant statistical methods, while evaluating the strengths and weaknesses of each modeling approach in capturing system dynamics based on the obtained results.

Critical Thinking and Reflection. Encourage students to critically analyze discrepancies between theory, simulation, and experimentation, fostering discussions on potential sources of error and strategies for improving model accuracy and reliability.

4 Implementation and Results

The first study presented in this section introduces a data-driven ML-based approach using polynomial regression (PR) for modeling PV panels, aimed at enhancing both accuracy and adaptability to environmental variables with a simple data-based method. The model is trained on both artificial and real datasets, which include solar irradiance, ambient temperature, and applied load data. Its primary objective is to estimate the electrical output of the PV system, namely voltage, current, and the produced power. The model's accuracy is evaluated using RMSE, a key metric that quantifies the difference between observed real values and predicted values, providing insight into the model's estimation error. By effectively capturing the non-linear relationships between environmental conditions and electrical outputs, the model demonstrates strong accuracy and generalization to unseen data. Experimental results further confirm the model's effectiveness by comparing it with on-site measurements, where a lower RMSE signifies higher predictive accuracy and a closer representation of the system's real-world behavior.

The PV panel used in this study is a 30-watt monocrystalline silicon module, employed for simulations, HIL testing, and real-world measurement of the voltage and current outputs. Model validation is carried out at the University of Applied Sciences and Arts Western Switzerland in Sion, as shown in Fig. 2. The validation process was conducted using a Speedgoat HIL testing system and a National Instruments (NI) CompactRIO controller [17].

Fig. 2. HIL and experimentation setup of a PV system at the University of Applied Sciences and Arts Western Switzerland in Sion/Switzerland [17].

The PR model, trained on an appropriate dataset, is validated over a period of 1 hour and 15 minutes, as shown in Fig. 3. During this period, irradiance fluctuates based on the sun's position, time of day, and cloud movements. The current and voltage outputs show that the load changes during the first quarter of the time, at 13:49, and again at 14:28, when both the load and irradiance fluctuate. During the cloudy period around 14:00, as irradiance drops, the voltage and current predictions from the model closely match the measured values. The RMSE obtained in this test indicates a low deviation between the estimated and measured values, with minimal error observed for both voltage and current measurements.

Fig. 3. Validation of the PR model in October 2023 in Sion/Switzerland: (a) irradiance, (b) measured and estimated voltage, (c) measured and estimated current [17].

The second study explores various ML approaches for modeling photovoltaic-thermal (PVT) systems. Its primary contribution lies in the development and application of advanced modeling techniques to predict the electrical and thermal power outputs of a PVT system. To validate the various developed models of the PVT system, real-time comparisons are conducted using a Beckhoff Programmable Logic Controller (PLC). The electrical and thermal subsystems of a PVT installation, implemented at the University of Applied Sciences and Arts Western Switzerland in Granges, are depicted in Fig. 4 [18].

Fig. 4. Experimentation setup of PVT system: (a) schematic [18], (b) real system in Granges/Switzerland.

For electrical power prediction, a dynamic model of the studied system is developed using an ML-based modeling technique, specifically PR. This method is widely recognized in system modeling for its simplicity and effectiveness in capturing system dynamics. Experimental data are collected in Granges between May 2 and May 11, 2024. As shown in Fig. 5, the training dataset consists of the initial 70% of the data within the specified range. The results demonstrate that the prediction error of the proposed model remains within 2% per unit (p.u). This error margin is within the acceptable range, underscoring the model's accuracy and reliability for predictive applications.

Fig. 5. The trained and predicted electrical power of the studied PVT system in May 2024, in Granges/Switzerland, based on the PR modeling approach [18].

For thermal power prediction, the autoregressive moving-average (ARMA) modeling method is compared with the long short-term memory (LSTM) model [20], a type of recurrent neural network (RNN), as well as with the conventional analytical approach [18]. The comparative analysis in Fig. 6 highlights the superior accuracy of data-driven methods compared to the traditional analytical approach, which also necessitates detailed knowledge of system parameters. In practice, obtaining precise values for internal components—such as the absorber layer thickness in PVT systems or the gap and conductivity parameters between layers—is challenging, making analytical modeling less feasible. Performance metrics reveal that among the data-driven techniques, the LSTM method achieves acceptable accuracy, while ARMA delivers comparable results with significantly lower computational complexity. This balance between accuracy and efficiency highlights the practicality of the ARMA approach for thermal power modeling.

Fig. 6. The comparison of the predicted thermal power of the studied PVT system using analytical and different data-driven modeling approaches, for 11th to 13th May 2024, in Granges/Switzerland [23].

Given the cases examined in this study and the implemented ML-based methods (PR, ARMA, and LSTM), these approaches can be classified into shallow and deep learning categories. Shallow learning methods, such as Polynomial Regression and ARMA, offer advantages in terms of simplicity, computational efficiency, and interpretability, making them well-suited for smaller datasets and problems with straightforward relationships. However, they may struggle with complex, high-dimensional data or unstructured inputs. In contrast, deep learning methods like LSTM excel at capturing intricate patterns and dependencies, particularly in time-series forecasting, but require higher computational resources and extensive training data. In general, the choice between shallow and deep learning ultimately depends on the complexity of the problem, the availability of data, and the required predictive accuracy [24].

5 Model Limitations and Applicability Scope

While the proposed framework effectively integrates analytical modeling, ML modeling, numerical simulation, HIL testing, and hands-on experimentation, it is essential to acknowledge the limitations and boundary conditions inherent to the models and methods. In this section some of these issues are mentioned.

- The analytical models are often built on idealized assumptions, such as linearity, time-invariance, and perfect input-output relationships. These assumptions simplify complex system dynamics but may lead to inaccuracies when applied to nonlinear or highly dynamic real-world systems. Additionally, parameter estimation for analytical models can be sensitive to noise and measurement errors, limiting their robustness.
- The effectiveness of data-driven models, such as PR, ARMA and LSTM, is highly dependent on the availability and quality of the training data. Inaccurate or incomplete datasets can introduce bias and reduce the model's predictive accuracy. Furthermore, overfitting remains a challenge, particularly for models trained on limited datasets with high variability.
- The numerical simulations rely on predefined boundary conditions and initial parameters that may not fully capture real-world operational variability. The environmental conditions (e.g., solar irradiance, ambient temperature) used in PV and PVT system simulations are based on specific geographic locations and time periods. This limits the generalizability of the results to other regions or climate conditions.
- HIL testing provides a valuable bridge between simulation and real-world experimentation, its scope is constrained by the hardware and software configurations. Certain dynamic behaviors and interactions might not be fully replicable due to limitations in sensor resolution, actuator performance, or computational power of the HIL platforms.
- Experimental validation, although critical for verifying model accuracy, is subject to operational constraints such as system disturbances, variability in environmental factors, and equipment precision. These challenges can introduce uncertainties and affect the reliability of the validation process.

6 Conclusion

The multi-faceted approach outlined in this study offers a significant opportunity to enhance students' comprehension of dynamic systems while equipping them with the skills necessary to address real-world engineering challenges. This methodology fosters critical thinking and problem-solving abilities by encouraging students to troubleshoot complex issues across various stages of system design and implementation. At the same time, it promotes technical proficiency through hands-on experience with industry-relevant tools and technologies, effectively bridging the gap between theoretical knowledge and practical application. Additionally, it encourages interdisciplinary understanding, helping students appreciate how different engineering disciplines interact and converge within the context of dynamic systems.

While the proposed framework demonstrates strong potential for improving engineering education, it is essential to acknowledge its limitations and scope of applicability. Analytical models, while foundational, rely on idealized assumptions that may not fully capture the complexity of real-world systems, especially under nonlinear or highly dynamic conditions. Similarly, the effectiveness of ML-based models depends heavily on the quality and diversity of training datasets, posing challenges in scenarios with limited or biased data. Furthermore, HIL testing and experimental validation, though invaluable for bridging theory and practice, are constrained by the resolution and precision of available hardware and the environmental conditions under which experiments are conducted. Addressing these limitations provides an avenue for further refinement of the framework, paving the way for more robust and adaptable educational tools.

This comprehensive educational strategy not only prepares students for the demands of modern engineering practices but also cultivates a deeper appreciation for the interconnected nature of engineering solutions. By addressing its limitations and carefully considering its scope of applicability, this framework offers a well-rounded approach to advancing engineering education and fostering the development of future-ready professionals.

Finally, an important direction for future work involves evaluating student feedback and measuring learning outcomes through surveys and real-world implementations. While this aspect has not yet been explored in the present study, conducting student acceptance surveys and assessing learning improvements using the proposed methodology could provide valuable insights. Such investigations would contribute to a deeper understanding of its effectiveness and enhance the practical relevance of future research in educational contexts.

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